

New records of planthoppers and leafhoppers from northern Poland (Hemiptera: Fulgoromorpha et Cicadomorpha)

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ABSTRACT. New records of planthoppers and leafhoppers from northern Poland.

The paper provides new distributional data for 88 species, recorded from three zoogeographical Regions – Baltic Coast, Masurian Lake District and Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland.

KEY WORDS: planthoppers, leafhoppers, zoogeography, faunistics, new records, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

The planthopper and leafhopper fauna of Poland comprises 552 species (GĘBICKI *et al.* 2013, WALCZAK *et al.* 2016), however, the knowledge of these insects in particular zoogeographical regions of Poland is very uneven. The regions quite well researched, with the number of species exceeding 300, are Mazovian Lowland (316), Upper Silesia (391), Krakowsko-Wieluńska Upland (374) and Western Beskidy Mountains (301). Other regions need further investigations, especially those with the number of species below 50% in respect to the total number, including Baltic Coast (259), Masurian Lake District (164) and Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland (239).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research were carried out at 10 localities within three zoogeographical regions of Poland: Baltic Coast (3 localities), Masurian Lake District (6 localities) and Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland (1 locality) in the years 2015 and 2016. The planthoppers and leafhoppers were collected using a sweep-net and preserved in 96% EtOH. Examined specimens are housed in plastic vials with labels.

Zoogeographic division of Poland (KFP) is presented according to *Katalog Fauny Polski* (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1973), physico-geographical division of Poland (RFG) follows KONDRACKI (2013).

LIST OF LOCALITIES

Baltic Coast (Pobrzeże Bałtyku) – KFP zoogeographical region:

[1] – Jarosławiec, 18–20.08.2016, leg. A. Stroiński, 54.53 N, 16.53 E; 0–4 m a.s.l., UTM

– WA94, RFG macroregion – Pobrzeże Koszalińskie, RFG mesoregion – Wybrzeże Słowińskie;

[2] – Dębki, 17–18.08.2015, leg. A. Stroiński, 54.82 N, 18.08 E, 0–1 m a.s.l., UTM – CF17, RFG macroregion – Pobrzeże Koszalińskie, RFG mesoregion – Wybrzeże Słowińskie;

[3] – Jastrzębia Góra, 28.08.2016, leg. P. Węgrzynowicz, 54.83 N, 18.32 E, 28–34 m a.s.l., UTM – CF27, RFG macroregion – Pobrzeże Gdańskie, RFG mesoregion – Pobrzeże Kaszubskie.

Masurian Lake District (Pojezierze Mazurskie) – KFP zoogeographical region:

[4] – Wysok, 04.07.2016, leg. A. Stroiński, 54.29 N, 21.54 E, 70–87 m a.s.l., UTM – EF31, RFG macroregion – Nizina Staropruska, RFG mesoregion – Nizina Sępolska;

[5] – Wydminy, 29–30.08.2015, leg. A. Stroiński, 53.97 N, 22.04 E, 136–137 m a.s.l., UTM – EE68, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Mazurskie, RFG mesoregion – Pojezierze Elckie;

[6] – vicinity of Jezioro Białe, 29–30.08.2015, leg. A. Stroiński, 53.96 N, 22.06 E, 138–139 m a.s.l., UTM – EE68, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Mazurskie, RFG mesoregion – Pojezierze Elckie;

[7] – Kałtki, 30.08.2015, leg. A. Stroiński, 53.93 N, 22.13 E, 128–130 m a.s.l., UTM – EE77, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Mazurskie, RFG mesoregion – Pojezierze Elckie;

[8] – meadow in Borecka Forest, 05.07.2016, leg. A. Stroiński, 54.17 N, 21.97 E, 174–176 m a.s.l., UTM – EF60, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Mazurskie, RFG mesoregion – Pojezierze Elckie;

[9] – Zielonki Forest District near Litygajno Lake in Borecka Forest, raised peat-bog, 05.07.2016, leg. A. Stroiński, 144–146 m a.s.l., UTM – EE79, 54.08 N 22.17 E, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Mazurskie, RFG mesoregion – Pojezierze Elckie.

Wielkopolska-Kujawska Lowland (Nizina Wielkopolsko-Kujawska) – KFP zoogeographical region:

[10] – Kobylniki, 22.08.2015, leg. A. Stroiński, 52.90 N, 18.15 E, 82–83 m a.s.l., UTM – CD06, RFG macroregion – Pojezierze Wielkopolskie, RFG mesoregion – Równina Inowrocławska.

LIST OF SPECIES

Below a list of 15 planthopper and 73 leafhopper species is presented, with the following numbers for particular regions: Baltic Coast – 53 species with 10 new for the region, Masurian Lake District – 58 species with 14 new for the region, Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland – 18 species with 2 new for the region. The taxa are arranged here in the same order as given in the check-list of planthoppers and leafhoppers of Poland (GĘBICKI *et al.* 2013)

FULGOROMORPHA EVANS, 1946

Cixiidae SPINOLA, 1839***Cixius nervosus*** (Linnaeus, 1758)

[2] - 1♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Delphacidae LEACH, 1815***Asiraca clavicornis*** (FABRICIUS, 1794)

[10] - 1♀, 22.08.2015.

Quite rare species with scattered localities across the whole country, however, most records dates back before 1976 (NAST 1976). The only recent finding is that from Poznań (Dębiec) from 2011 (Polish Biodiversity Information Network, www.hemiptera.ksib.pl). Probably polyphagous species, associated with sunny, moderately dry to dry, usually disturbed sites. As the species is strikingly coloured and easy to identify, it may indicate that its population declined in central Europe during the last few decades (NICKEL 2003).

Kelisia ribauti WAGNER, 1938

[1] - 31♂♂ 37♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Stenocranus major (KIRSCHBAUM, 1868)

[1] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 3♂♂ 3♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [5] - 4♂♂ 11♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 6♂♂ 4♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂ 4♀♀, 30.08.2015.

The new species for the regions – Baltic Coast, Masurian Lake District.

Conomelus anceps (GERMAR, 1821)

[1] - 87♂♂ 93♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 39♂♂ 82♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 1♀, 04.07.2016; [6] - 166♂♂ 236♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Laodelphax striatella (FALLÉN, 1826)

[2] - 1♂, 17-18.08.2015.

Muellerianella extrusa (SCOTT, 1871)

[5] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015.

Acanthodelphax spinosa (FIEBER, 1866)

[1] - 15♂♂ 5♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Dicranotropis hamata (BOHEMAN, 1847)

[4] - 1♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂ 3♀♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Dictyophara europaea (LINNAEUS, 1767)

[10] - 1♀, 22.08.2015.

Xanthodelphax straminea (STÅL, 1858)

[1] - 3♂♂ 7♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

Paradelphacodes paludosa (FLOR, 1861)

[9] - 1♂ 1♀, 05.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Javesella pellucida (FABRICIUS, 1794)

[1] - 13♂♂ 17♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Ribautodelphax albostrata (FIEBER, 1866)

[1] - 8♂♂ 6♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [5] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂, 30.08.2015.

Ribautodelphax collina (BOHEMAN, 1847)

[1] - 18♂♂ 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

CICADOMORPHA EVANS, 1946

Aphrophoridae AMYOT et AUDINET-SERVILLE, 1843***Aphrophora alni*** (FALLÉN, 1805)

[3] - 1♀, 28.08.2015; [4] - 2♂♂ 3♀♀, 04.07.2016; [7] - 1♀, 30.08.2015.

Aphrophora similis LETHIERRY, 1888

[9] - 14♂♂ 20♀♀, 05.07.2016.

The specimens from this locality supplemented with zoogeographical and bionomy data were published in the earlier paper by STROIŃSKI *et al.* (2016).***Philaenus spumarius*** (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[1] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 5♂♂ 8♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 18♀♀ 19♂♂, 04.07.2016; [5] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 7♂♂ 10♀♀, 30.08.2015; [8] - 1♀, 06.07.2016; [10] - 4♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Neophilaenus campestris (FALLÉN, 1805)

[1] - 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Neophilaenus lineatus (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[1] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 20♂♂ 23♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [7] - 20♂♂ 23♀♀, 30.08.2015; [9] - 1♂, 05.07.2016.

Lepyronia coleoptrata (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[4] - 6♀♀ 7♂♂, 04.07.2016.

Cicadellidae LATREILLE, 1802***Macropsis cerea*** (GERMAR, 1837)

[1] - 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Macropsis infuscata (J. SAHLBERG, 1871)

[10] - 2♀♀, 22.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland.

Megophthalmus scanicus (FALLÉN, 1806)

[1] - 3♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 1♂ 1♀, 04.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Agallia brachyptera (BOHEMAN, 1847)

[1] - 6♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [5] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 5♀♀, 30.08.2015; [8] - 1♂, 06.07.2016.

Anaceratagallia ribauti (OSSIANNILSSON, 1938)

[2] - 2♂♂ 1♀, 17-18.08.2015; [5] - 3♂♂ 10♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 3♂♂ 10♀♀, 30.08.2015.

The new species for the regions – Baltic Coast, Masurian Lake District.

Several males from Wydminy (locality 5) and Kałtki (locality 7) in Masurian Lake District revealed some characters of the male genitalia similar to described from Latvia *Anaceratagallia lithuanica* VILBASTE, 1974 – tip of aedeagus with broadening and appendage of anal tube two-tipped with shallow incision (VILBASTE 1974). *A. lithuanica* was described on the basis of one male and until now it has been known exclusively from locus typicus (Nemenčinė, Lithuania) thus its taxonomic status is uncertain (NICKEL, pers. comm.). The discovery of the specimens with similar genital characters from the same region (in distance of 260 km) may support the validity of the species, however, further studies are required.

Idiocerus similis KIRSCHBAUM, 1868

[4] - 1♂, 04.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Idiocerus stigmatalis LEWIS, 1834

[2] - 2♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [6] - 3♂♂ 4♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Populicerus confusus (FLOR, 1861)

[1] - 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Cicadella viridis (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[1] - 5♂♂ 7♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 11♂♂ 53♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 04.07.2016; [6] - 3♂♂ 12♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 11♂♂ 53♀♀, 30.08.2015; [9] - 18♂♂ 12♀♀, 05.07.2016.

Dikraneura variata HARDY, 1850

[6] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Forcipata citrinella (ZETTERSTEDT, 1828)

[5] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♂ 4♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Notus flavipennis (ZETTERSTEDT, 1828)

[1] - 1♂ 1♀, 18-20.08.2015; [6] - 1♂ 1♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Empoasca pteridis (DAHLBOM, 1850)

[6] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015; [10] - 10♂♂ 11♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Chlorita paolii (OSSIANNILSSON, 1939)

[1] - 2♂♂ 5♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 7♂♂ 2♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 28♂♂ 70♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 9♂♂ 13♀♀, 30.08.2015.

Eupteryx calcarata OSSIANNILSSON, 1936

[10] - 4♂♂ 6♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Eupteryx florida RIBAUT, 1936

[10] - 1♂ 4♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Eupteryx notata CURTIS, 1937

[7] - 1♂, 30.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Eupteryx vittata (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[5] - 1♀, 29-30.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Aphrodes aestuarina (EDWARDS, 1908)

[1] - 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

The taxonomic status of this species was unclear until the work of BLUEMEL *et al.* (2014), who confirmed *A. aestuarina* as behaviourally, genetically and morphologically distinct species. At present this taxon is only known from coastal regions of the North and Baltic

Sea, where it is probably associated with coastal saltmarshes and moderately saline meadows and pastures (NICKEL 2003). Some old records from the Polish part of Baltic coast identified as *Aphrodes bicincta* (SCHRANK, 1776) probably refer to this species.

Aphrodes bicincta (SCHRANK, 1776)

[2] - 1♂ 6♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 20♂♂ 9♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 1♂ 9♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂, 30.08.2015; [8] - 2♂♂, 06.07.2016.

Aphrodes makarovi ZACHVATKIN, 1948

[10] - 3♀♀, 22.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland.

Planaphrodes nigrita (KIRSCHBAUM, 1868)

[1] - 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

Anoscopus albifrons (LINNAEUS, 1758)

[1] - 1♂ 1♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Fieberiella septentrionalis WAGNER, 1963

[5] - 3♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Nealiturus fenestratus (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1834)

[8] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 06.07.2016.

Balclutha punctata (FABRICIUS, 1775)

[1] - 8♂♂ 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 5♂♂ 9♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [6] - 4♂♂ 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂ 3♀♀, 30.08.2015; [9] - 2♂♂, 05.07.2016.

Macrosteles cristatus (RIBAUT, 1927)

[2] - 1♂ 3♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Macrosteles laevis (RIBAUT, 1927)

[3] - 1♂, 28.08.2015; [5] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 4♂♂ 5♀♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 23♂♂ 14♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Macrosteles variatus (FALLÉN, 1806)

[10] - 1♂, 22.08.2015.

Macrosteles septemnotatus (FALLÉN, 1806)

[2] - 2♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

Allygus communis (FERRARI, 1882)

[9] - 2♂♂, 05.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Allygus mixtus (FABRICIUS, 1794)

[5] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [8] - 3♀♀, 06.07.2016.

Orientus ishidae (MATSUMURA, 1902)

[3] - 1♀, 28.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

This is an alien species in Europe, originating from Southeast Asia, recently recorded also for Poland (KLEJDYSZ *et al.* 2017) from the following regions: Mazovian Lowland (Warszawa), Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland (Poznań), Krakowsko-Wieluńska Upland (Kraków, Częstochowa) and Western Sudetes Mts (Lewin Kłodzki). In Poland, most records are from urban parks and orchards; collected on *Coryllus avellana*, *Amelanchier spicata*, *Crataegus*, *Ulmus* and *Quercus*.

Graphocraerus ventralis (FALLÉN, 1806)

[1] - 3♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 6♀♀, 04.07.2016; [8] - 3♀♀, 06.07.2016.

Hesium domino (REUTER, 1880)

[4] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 04.07.2016; [7] - 3♀♀, 30.08.2015.

Macustus grisescens (ZETTERSTEDT, 1828)

[9] - 1♂, 05.07.2016.

Athysanus argentarius METCALF, 1955

[1] - 3♂♂ 21♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 1♂, 3♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 10♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [8] - 1♀, 06.07.2016; [10] - 2♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Stictocoris picturatus (C. SAHLBERG, 1842)

[8] - 1♂♂ 3♀♀, 06.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Euscelidius schenckii (KIRSCHBAUM, 1868)

[7] - 2♂♂, 30.08.2015.

Conosanus obsoletus (KIRSCHBAUM, 1858)

[1] - 5♂♂ 12♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 9♂♂ 43♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [7] - 3♂♂ 22♀♀, 30.08.2015.

Euscelis incisus (KIRSCHBAUM, 1858)

[1] - 1♂, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 15♂♂ 13♀♀, 04.07.2016.

Cicadula frontalis (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1835)

[2] - 5♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Cicadula quadrinotata (FABRICIUS, 1794)

[1] - 23♂♂ 6♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 21♂♂ 10♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [6] - 4♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Cicadula persimilis (EDWARDS, 1920)

[4] - 1♂ 3♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 1♂, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 2♂♂, 22.08.2015.

Elymana sulphurella (ZETTERSTEDT, 1828)

[1] - 1♂ 11♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 1♂ 1♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 10♂♂, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [8] - 2♂♂ 1♀, 06.07.2016; [10] - 3♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Rhopalopyx vitripennis (FLOR, 1861)

[5] - 64♂♂ 110♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂, 30.08.2015.

Rhopalopyx preysleri (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1838)

[1] - 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 2♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Eupelix cuspidata (FABRICIUS, 1775)

[1] - 4♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 04.07.2016; [7] - 1♀, 30.08.2015; [8] - 2♂♂, 06.07.2016.

Doratura homophyla (FLOR, 1861)

[4] - 1♂, 04.07.2016.

Doratura stylata (BOHEMAN, 1847)

[1] - 68♂♂ 106♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 11♂♂ 15♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 3♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 7♂♂ 10♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♂ 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [8] - 8♂♂ 6♀♀, 06.07.2016; [10] - 5♂♂ 6♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Deltocephalus pulicaris (FALLÉN, 1806)

[5] - 7♂♂ 6♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 30.08.2015.

Recilia coronifer (MARSHALL, 1866)

[1] - 1♂, 18-20.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

Arocephalus languidus (FLOR, 1861)

[4] - 1♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 31♂♂ 13♀♀, 29-30.08.2015.

Arocephalus longiceps (KIRSCHBAUM, 1868)

[2] - 1♂, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 1♂, 04.07.2016.

The new species for the regions – Baltic Coast, Masurian Lake District.

Psammotettix alienus (DAHLBOM, 1850)

[1] - 4♂♂ 5♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [7] - 4♂♂ 2♀♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 6♂♂ 7♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Psammotettix confinis (DAHLBOM, 1850)

[1] - 12♂♂ 13♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [5] - 26♂♂ 20♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 9♂♂ 15♀♀, 30.08.2015.

Psammotettix nodosus (RIBAUT, 1925)

[2] - 11♂♂ 5♀♀, 17-18.08.2015.

Errastunus ocellaris (FALLÉN, 1806)

[1] - 62♂♂ 39♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 5♂♂ 9♀♀, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 1♂ 1♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 15♂♂ 19♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 1♂ 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 11♂♂ 28♀♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 8♂♂ 5♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Turrutus socialis (FLOR, 1861)

[10] - 1♂, 22.08.2015.

Jassargus alpinus (THEN, 1896) ssp. ***neglectus*** THEN, 1896

[9] - 2♂♂ 1♀, 05.07.2016.

There are four subspecies distinguished for this taxon: ssp. *neglectus* THEN, 1896 known from European mountains (Eastern Alps, Bohemian Forest, Western Carpathians, Sudetes) and eastern and northern Europe (Sweden, Norway); ssp. *alpinus* THEN, 1896 known from north-eastern Alps and Harz Mountains; ssp. *alemanicus* WAGNER, 1958 confined to central Alps (North Tirol) and German Black Forest; ssp. *cebennicus* RIBAUT, 1952 restricted to the Central Massif in France. In Poland, the subspecies *neglectus* is known from scattered localities in the Masurian Lake District, Upper Silesia, Krakowsko-Wieluńska Upland, Sudetes and Polish part of Carpathians. In Germany, the species is found in damp to moist, moderately shady to sunny sites of montane areas, usually in open forests, clearings, pastures and meadows. Host plants are various grasses (NICKEL 2003).

Jassargus flori (FIEBER, 1869)

[8] - 4♂♂ 6♀♀, 06.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Jassargus pseudocellaris (FLOR, 1861)

[1] - 126♂♂ 88♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

Verdanus abdominalis (FABRICIUS, 1803)

[2] - 1♀, 17-18.08.2015; [5] - 1♀, 29-30.08.2015; [8] - 2♂♂ 6♀♀, 06.07.2016.

Arthaldeus arenarius REMANE, 1960

[1] - 1♂ 2♀♀, 18-20.08.2015.

The new species for the region – Baltic Coast.

Arthaldeus pascuellus (FALLÉN, 1826)

[1] - ♂♂ ♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [2] - 3♂♂, 17-18.08.2015; [4] - 1♂ 11♀♀, 04.07.2016; [5] - 28♂♂ 11♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [6] - 2♂♂ 2♀♀, 29-30.08.2015; [7] - 1♂ 1♀, 30.08.2015; [10] - 4♂♂ 6♀♀, 22.08.2015.

Cosmotettix panzeri (FLOR, 1861)

[9] - 6♂♂ 8♀♀, 05.07.2016.

The new species for the region – Masurian Lake District.

Henschia collina (BOHEMAN, 1850)

[1] - 3♂♂ 4♀♀, 18-20.08.2015; [4] - 3♂♂ 3♀♀, 04.07.2016.

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STRESZCZENIE

Nowe stwierdzenia piewików z obszaru północnej Polski (Hemiptera: Fulgoromorpha et Cicadomorpha)

W pracy podano nowe dane o rozmieszczeniu 88 gatunków piewików na obszarze północnej Polski – regiony zoogeograficzne wg *Katalogu Fauny Polski*: Pobrzeże Bałtyku (stanowiska 1-3), Pojezierze Mazurskie (stanowiska 4-9) i Nizina Wielkopolsko-Kujawska (stanowisko 10). Dla poszczególnych regionów stwierdzono następującą liczbę gatunków: Pobrzeże Bałtyku – 53 gatunki, w tym 10 nowych dla regionu; Pojezierze Mazurskie – 58 gatunków, w tym 14 nowych dla regionu; Nizina Wielkopolsko-Kujawska – 18 gatunków, w tym 2 nowe dla regionu.

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